

Deadline-Aware Bandwidth Allocation for Semantic Generative Communication with Diffusion Models

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Abstract—The importance of Radio Access Network (RAN) in support Artificial Intelligence (AI) application services has grown significantly, underscoring the need for an integrated approach that considers not only network efficiency but also AI performance. In this paper we focus on a semantic generative communication (SGC) framework for image inpainting application. Specifically, the transmitter sends semantic information, including semantic masks and textual descriptions, while the receiver applies a conditional diffusion model to a shared base image, using this information as conditioning data to generate the intended image. In this framework, we propose a bandwidth allocation scheme designed to maximize bandwidth efficiency while ensuring generation performance. This approach is based on our finding of a “*Semantic Deadline*”—the minimum time that conditioning data is required to be injected to meet a given performance threshold—within the multi-modal SGC framework. Given this observation, the proposed scheme allocates limited bandwidth so that each semantic information can be transmitted within the corresponding semantic deadline. Experimental results corroborate that the proposed bandwidth allocation scheme achieves higher generation performance in terms of PSNR for a given bandwidth compared to traditional schemes that do not account for semantic deadlines.

Index Terms—Generative AI, diffusion model, image inpainting, semantic communication, bandwidth allocation.

I. INTRODUCTION

The emergence of Artificial Intelligence Generated Content (AIGC) services has gained significant attention in recent years, driven by their transformative potential across diverse industries. These services, which leverage generative AI to generate text, images, videos, and audio, offer unprecedented efficiency and creativity in content creation. These advances in AIGC have led to the attention of semantic generative communication (SGC) frameworks to support this application in wireless networks, where the transmitter transmits semantic information and the receiver directly or indirectly utilizes it to generate the intended image through generative AI [1]–[4]. Despite this intensive interest, existing research lacks a communication system design that accounts for both network efficiency and the unique characteristics of AIGC services. This is because comprehending the correlation between semantic information and the intended image in generative AI is highly complex, particularly when dealing with multi-modal semantic information.

To explore a multi-modal AIGC framework, our research focuses on designing uplinks over SGC, specifically for image inpainting applications using a conditional diffusion model. In this framework, the transmitter’s objective is to deliver the

intended image to the receiver—not by directly transmitting it, as in traditional communication, but by sending semantic information as in semantic communication. This information, derived from a semantic mask and textual description, conveys the transmitter’s intent—specifically, how the base image (shared between transmitter and receiver) should be modified. The receiver then generates the intended image by applying the diffusion model, using the base image as input and the semantic information as conditioning data.

In the multimodal SGC framework described above, we empirically find that each piece of semantic information has a specific “*Semantic Deadline*”. Delivering semantic information to the receiver within this deadline maximizes bandwidth efficiency while ensuring the desired generation performance. Building on this finding, we propose a bandwidth allocation scheme for the uplink that accounts for both AIGC performance and communication efficiency. Through numerical evaluation, we demonstrate that the proposed scheme achieves the highest PSNR at a given bandwidth.

A. Related Works and Motivations

Recent studies have increasingly explored multi-modal data processing in wireless communication. In [5], the authors propose a network design methodology that improves Virtual Reality (VR) service performance by considering the interplay between visual and haptic modalities. More recent work, such as [6], examines AI/ML-based services by decomposing image transmission into two modalities and analyzing their impact on the final output. Similarly, [7] introduces an adaptive modulation and coding scheme that adjusts to channel conditions for each modality, enhancing image reconstruction fidelity. While these studies advance multi-modal transmission techniques, they largely treat the computational processes within these services as independent components. In contrast, our work integrates transmission and computation by leveraging the structural characteristics of diffusion models. This holistic approach offers a deeper understanding of the interplay between communication and generative AI, leading to more effective and interpretable results.

B. Contributions

- The contributions of this work are summarized as follows.
- We introduce and define the concept of a “*Semantic Deadline*” as a novel metric to assess the relationship between each semantic information and the final output.

This concept establishes the latest point in the iterative computation process by which each semantic information must be received, providing a quantifiable standard to drive network optimization effectively.

- Based on this analysis, we propose a heuristic solution for uplink wireless resource allocation. The superiority of this solution is demonstrated through comparisons with baseline approaches that do not account for semantic information differences with final outcome.
- Through an integrated network design, our novel approach to wireless resource allocation enhances wireless resource efficiency. The simulation results show the impact of this approach, demonstrating its potential to drive more effective future network designs.

II. SYSTEM MODEL AND PROBLEM DESCRIPTION

In this section, we present the SGC framework for multi-modal image inpainting. We consider a network with a single transmitter and a single receiver, where the receiver is equipped with a Stable Diffusion architecture [8]. The transmitter and receiver share a base image, which serves as the foundation for generating the intended image. To facilitate image inpainting, the transmitter sends two types of semantic information—semantic masks and textual descriptions—each transmitted over separate orthogonal channels. The base image is then dynamically modified using a conditional diffusion model, guided by the received multi-modal inputs. Our objective is to optimize bandwidth allocation for semantic information transmission while maintaining high-quality image inpainting, even in resource-constrained environments. Each of these processes will be explained in detail in the following subsections, and the overall framework is illustrated in Fig. 1.

A. Transmitter

The transmitter delivers each semantic information in the following manner. The semantic mask represents the areas of the image that need to be modified in white, while the areas that should remain unchanged are in black. Let this semantic mask image be denoted as M_s . The transmitter encodes the original mask M_s with source coding to reduce the data size which is then transmitted to the receiver. The textual description is represented by M_l . A description of a part of the image to transform. The M_l is encoded into an 8-bit binary string using ASCII encoding. Thus, the transmitter sends two modalities, M_s and M_l , to the receiver. The transmission data sizes for these modalities are denoted as D_s and D_l , respectively.

B. Transmission Model

The semantic mask M_s and textual description M_l are transmitted over two orthogonal wireless channels to ensure independent and interference-free communication. Each orthogonal channel is assumed to experience Rayleigh fading and block fading during the transmission period. Under these

assumptions, the receiver get each semantic information as follows:

$$\tilde{M}_i = h_i M_i + n_i, \quad i \in \{s, l\} \quad (1)$$

where $h_i \in \mathbb{C}$ represents the channel gain coefficient and $n_i \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \sigma^2)$ is the additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN). We assumed the received signal \tilde{M}_i can be effectively compensated for using a channel equalizer at the receiver. This allows the transmitted data to be restored with minimal distortion, resulting in \hat{M}_i , which closely approximates the original signal M_i .

Although the receiver can minimize distortion for each data through appropriate channel equalization, independent fading conditions of each channel introduce variations in reception times. These differences in channel conditions result in time delays between the complete reception of each semantic information. The time required for full reception can be expressed as:

$$t_i = \frac{D_i}{B_i \log_2(1 + \gamma_i)}, \quad i \in \{s, l\} \quad (2)$$

where $\gamma_i = \frac{|h_i|^2 P}{N_0}$ represents the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of each independent channel, where P denotes the power spectral density and N_0 represents the noise power spectral density. It is assumed that the transmitter has sufficient power resources to adjust P , ensuring reliable communication despite varying channel conditions. Here, B_i denotes bandwidth allocated for the i -th semantic information transmission ($\sum_{i \in \{s, l\}} B_i = B$).

C. Receiver

The receiver is equipped with an image inpainting model. Once the connection is established between the transmitter and receiver, the receiver initiates the reverse diffusion process for image inpainting. This process begins with the starting latent variable $Z_{t=0}$, generated based on $\mathcal{N}(0, 1)$. As the semantic mask and textual description are received asynchronously, each with a delay t_i , the reverse diffusion process is divided into four distinct stages ① ~ ④.

- ① $t < t_s$ & $t < t_l$: This is the case when neither the semantic mask nor the textual description has arrived at the receiving end. Accordingly, the reverse diffusion process can be expressed as follows:

$$Z_{t+\omega} = p_\theta(Z_t, M_s^{random}, M_l^{random}).$$

- ② $t \geq t_s$ & $t < t_l$: In this case, the semantic mask is received, but the textual description is not. Consequently, the reverse diffusion process can be expressed as follows:

$$Z_{t+\omega} = p_\theta(Z_t, \hat{M}_s, M_l^{random}).$$

- ③ $t < t_s$ & $t \geq t_l$: In this case, the textual description is received, but the semantic mask is not. Consequently, the reverse diffusion process can be expressed as follows:

$$Z_{t+\omega} = p_\theta(Z_t, M_s^{random}, \hat{M}_l).$$

Fig. 1. System diagram illustrating the overall process. The transmitter sends each semantic information, while the receiver’s internal image inpainting process is depicted, highlighting the asynchronous reception.

- ④ $t \geq t_s$ & $t \geq t_l$: In this case, all data is successfully received. The reverse diffusion process can be expressed as follows:

$$\mathbf{Z}_{t+\omega} = p_{\theta}(\mathbf{Z}_t, \hat{M}_s, \hat{M}_l).$$

The function p_{θ} represents the U-Net within the Stable Diffusion model with weight parameter θ . The variable ω denotes the time required for a single reverse diffusion step. Additionally, M_s^{random} and M_l^{random} denote a random semantic mask and textual description used as a placeholder. The reverse diffusion process iterates over a predefined number of steps within a total time of T , resulting in the final variable \mathbf{Z}_T . Due to the asynchronous of t_s and t_l , we denote the generated \mathbf{Z}_T as $\mathbf{Z}_T(t_s, t_l)$. The $\mathbf{Z}_T(t_s, t_l)$ is then fed into the VAE decoder at the receiver to generate the final image, denoted by I .

D. Performance Metric

In the proposed image inpainting framework, the quality of generated content is influenced by the asynchronous arrival times of each semantic information. To quantify this impact, we adopted an ideal scenario, where there are no delays, as the baseline for comparison. To this end, we define the ideal latent variable as $\mathbf{Z}_T^* = \mathbf{Z}_T(0, 0)$. We measured the Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR) between the ideal \mathbf{Z}_T^* and the delayed $\mathbf{Z}_T(t_s, t_l)$. The equation is as follows.

$$\text{PSNR}(t_s, t_l) = 10 \cdot \log_{10} \left(\frac{\text{MAX}^2}{\|\mathbf{Z}_T^* - \mathbf{Z}_T(t_s, t_l)\|_2} \right) \quad (3)$$

where the $\text{MAX} = 6$, as the range of the latent values we are dealing with spans from -6 to 6 .

E. Problem Description

In this framework, our objective is to determine the optimal bandwidth allocation scheme between two types of semantic information to maximize PSNR. Naturally, allocating more

bandwidth to semantic information reduces transmission time, as described in (2). Ideally, with infinite bandwidth, image inpainting performance is maximized since t_s and t_l approach zero, as per (3). However, since B is practically limited, a trade-off exists between t_s and t_l , while the precise impact of these variables on PSNR remains unknown.

Thus, we define the objective function as follows, reflecting the maximization of image inpainting performance under given bandwidth constraints:

$$\mathbf{P1:} \quad \max_{\{B_s, B_l\}} \text{PSNR}(t_s, t_l) \quad (4)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \sum_{i \in \{s, l\}} B_i \leq B, \quad (4a)$$

$$B_i \geq 0, \quad i \in \{s, l\} \quad (4b)$$

where (4a) represents the bandwidth constraint, and (4b) ensures non-negative bandwidth allocation.

III. PROPOSED SOLUTION

The performance of image inpainting is difficult to explicitly relate to the control variables B_s and B_l . This is due to the influence of various factors, such as the unique characteristics of each sample, the content of the textual description, and the scope of semantic masking. These factors collectively impact performance, making problem **P1** challenging to solve directly. Therefore, detailed observations and a corresponding reformulation are required to effectively address this complexity.

A. Semantic Deadline in Image Inpainting

To address this challenge, we conducted extensive experiments to explore whether the objective function of problem **P1** could be reformulated to establish an explicit relationship with the control variables B_s and B_l . From these experiments, we derived a key insight: the average quality graph exhibits a concave, monotonically decreasing trend within the meaningful quality range ($\varepsilon \geq \varepsilon_{\text{th}}$). Accordingly, let $\mathcal{G}_{\varepsilon}$ denote the

Fig. 2. The left graph shows the average $\text{PSNR}(t_s, t_l)$ result. The right graph illustrates the results of semantic deadline clipping with threshold $\varepsilon = \{0.95, 0.85, 0.75, 0.65\}$, aimed at inferring the relationship between the modalities in $\text{PSNR}(t_s, t_l)$.

set of all points (t_s, t_l) that satisfy a threshold ε . Then, the following condition holds:

$$\mathcal{G}_\varepsilon \subseteq \mathcal{G}_{\dot{\varepsilon}} \quad \text{if and only if} \quad \varepsilon > \dot{\varepsilon}.$$

Within the set \mathcal{G}_ε , the semantic deadline point $(t_{s,\varepsilon}, t_{l,\varepsilon})$ is defined as the point that maximizes the Euclidean distance from the origin $(0, 0)$.

$$(t_{s,\varepsilon}, t_{l,\varepsilon}) = \max_{(t_s, t_l) \in \mathcal{G}_\varepsilon} \|(t_s, t_l)\|_2. \quad (5)$$

By tracking these semantic deadline point $(t_{s,\varepsilon}, t_{l,\varepsilon})$ as ε varies, we construct a set \mathcal{G}^* .

$$\mathcal{G}^* := \{(t_{s,\varepsilon}, t_{l,\varepsilon}) \mid \varepsilon \in [\varepsilon_{\text{th}}, 1]\} \quad (6)$$

The curve formed by the points within the set \mathcal{G}^* is defined as the “*Semantic Deadline*”. This semantic deadline serves as a key element that enables the relaxation of the problem **P1**. Fig. 2 provides a visual illustration of the semantic deadline.

B. Problem Transformation

Leveraging the semantic deadline, we decomposed **P1** into two subproblems. First, we aim to determine the maximum achievable threshold ε^* under the given bandwidth constraints by solving **P2**. In addressing **P2**, which is inherently a discrete optimization using (4), we note that the bandwidth constraint does not necessarily satisfy equality in its feasible solutions. Thus, we solve subproblem **P3** to resolve the optimal allocation values B_s^* and B_l^* , ensuring that the bandwidth constraint is met as an equality condition.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{P2} : \max_{\varepsilon} \quad & \text{PSNR}(t_{s,\varepsilon}, t_{l,\varepsilon}) \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & (4a), (4b). \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

To find the ε^* , it is necessary to solve (5) for every ε within the range $[\varepsilon_{\text{th}}, 1]$. If ε were treated as a continuous variable over this range, the computational complexity would be infinite. To mitigate this, we discretize $[\varepsilon_{\text{th}}, 1]$ into K discrete values, reducing the complexity to $O(T^2K)$, where T represents the total denoise steps of the diffusion model.

Fig. 3. Semantic deadline-aware optimization approach with an example image. Each point represents the initial position set by the semantic deadline point at different thresholds. Semantic deadline indicate the optimization trajectory, illustrating the progression toward improved image inpainting performance.

As ε^* is determined by solving **P2**, we construct **P3** as below:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{P3} : \max_{\{B_s, B_l\}} \quad & \text{PSNR}(t_{s,\varepsilon^*} + \hat{t}_s, t_{l,\varepsilon^*} + \hat{t}_l) \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & (4a), (4b). \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where \hat{B}_i represents the additional wireless resource allocated to semantic information i beyond the determined bandwidth according to ε^* .

C. Semantic Deadline-Aware Resource Allocation

In this section, we derive the optimal resource allocations B_s^* and B_l^* by solving **P2** and **P3**. First, the optimal solution to **P2** allows us to determine the minimum image inpainting quality threshold, ε^* , under the given constraints. Consequently, the minimum bandwidth allocated to each semantic information is $B_{i,\varepsilon^*} = \frac{D_i}{t_{i,\varepsilon^*} \log_2(1+\gamma_i)}$, $i \in \{s, l\}$. To solve **P2**, we use the set of K discrete semantic deadline points, denoted as $\mathcal{G}^*(K)$, which is obtained with a computational complexity of $O(T^2K)$. After obtaining $\mathcal{G}^*(K)$, ε^* can be obtained with an additional complexity of $O(K)$. As K increases, **P2** provides **P3** with a more refined optimization scheme, as detailed in the following.

To solve **P3**, we employed a heuristic approach guided by the obtained semantic deadlines $\mathcal{G}^*(K)$ in **P2**. This approach optimizes the allocation of the remaining bandwidth by moving from the minimal resource allocation point toward the next threshold semantic deadline point along the shortest path. By using semantic deadline $\mathcal{G}^*(K)$ that solved by **P2** and

Fig. 4. The error bar graph illustrates trends in semantic deadline points across variables affecting image inpainting in threshold $\varepsilon = 0.85$.

assumption in section III-A, this approach ensures efficient utilization of the additional resources. The derived optimal bandwidth allocation of each semantic information B_i^* is given by

$$B_i^* = B_{i,\varepsilon^*} + B' \left(\frac{\alpha_{i,\varepsilon^*}}{\sum_i^{\{s,l\}} \alpha_{i,\varepsilon^*}} \right), \forall i \in \{s, l\} \quad (9)$$

where B_{i,ε^*} represents the minimum allocated bandwidth resource obtained by **P2**. And $B_{i,grad}$ is given by $\alpha_{i,\varepsilon^*} = \left(\frac{1}{t_{i,\varepsilon'}} - \frac{1}{t_{i,\varepsilon^*}} \right) \frac{D_i}{\log_2(1+\gamma_i)}$. Where ε' means the next threshold value compared to ε^* .

IV. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

A. Environment Settings

The experiments were conducted using an image inpainting model based on Stable Diffusion. The total number of reverse denoising steps T was set to 20, and the guidance scale was set to 12. In our simulation environment with an RTX 3090 GPU, the time to complete a single reverse diffusion step $\omega = 0.05$ second. We used the *CelebA-HQ* dataset [9]. It includes two types of images: high-quality facial images X_0 and specific facial features masked image M_s such as hair, eyes, and mouth masked in white against a black background. The textual description M_l were randomly generated to describe facial features corresponding to M_s . The average data size of the semantic mask D_s was 4KB when compressed in PNG format, while the textual description had an average size of 1KB when compressed using 8-bit ASCII encoding. For the experiments, we assumed that the independent wireless channel gain followed a Gamma distribution with unit mean and a scale factor of 2.

B. Variance of Semantic Deadline

To address the inherent ambiguity in the relationship between the objective function $\text{PSNR}(\cdot)$ and the control variables $\{B_s, B_l\}$, we introduced the concept of a semantic deadline. To validate the general applicability of semantic deadline, we

Fig. 5. Image inpainting performance under given bandwidth constraints. The figure presents a comparison across four cases: two benchmarks and the proposed algorithm with quantization parameters $K = \{4, 20\}$.

examined how it varies under different conditions, including base image characteristics, text prompts, and semantic masking areas. Fig. 4 illustrates these results, showing the distribution of semantic deadline points at $\varepsilon = 0.9$ across these variables. Although the values of the semantic deadline points varied according to each factor, a consistent relationship emerged between the two modalities. This consistency confirms that, with an appropriate K discrete value, the proposed algorithm can maintain reliable performance across diverse conditions.

C. Performance Gains under Equivalent Bandwidth

To verify the effectiveness of our proposed algorithm, we established two benchmark for comparison. Benchmark 1 aims to maximize the overall throughput across the independent channels. Moreover, benchmark 2 allocates the available bandwidth resources to minimize the total transmission time of each semantic information i within the given bandwidth constraints. Benchmark 2, in addition to considering the transmission channel for each semantic information i as in Benchmark 1, also takes into account the data size. For evaluation, we tested 4 configurations: the two benchmark algorithms and our proposed algorithm with discrete values $K = 4$ and $K = 20$. As shown in Fig. 5, our algorithm with $K = 20$ guarantee the highest performance for overall bandwidth condition. Benchmark 1, which optimizes solely based on channel state without regard to semantic information characteristics, yielded the poorest performance. This result underscores the importance of accounting for data attributes in recent semantic communication network. As the discrete value K increases, the performance of the proposed algorithm gradually improves and then converges, as the precise optimization trajectory—modeled by the continuous semantic deadline—reaches a stable direction for bandwidth resource optimization.

Fig. 6. Visual comparison of image inpainting results obtained using the proposed algorithm. The “Ideal” case represents an optimal result without considering wireless environments, with closer resemblance indicating better performance. In most cases, the proposed algorithm with a quantization parameter of $K = 20$ closely approximates the ideal outcome.

D. Visual Quality of the Proposed Algorithm

To further validate the effectiveness of our proposed algorithm, we visualized its outcomes in Fig. 6 to illustrate the impact of its quantitative advantages on actual image results. The visualization is in case with a bandwidth resource $B = 0.3\text{MHz}$, where the transmission channel states for each semantic information are set at $\gamma_s = 2.3\text{dB}$ and $\gamma_l = 3.5\text{dB}$. The visual results reveal distinctions based on discrete value K , which previously showed only marginal differences in numerical analysis. For benchmark 1 and 2, textual descriptions were not transmitted within the text semantic deadline, resulting in placeholder’s wrong image inpainting quality. These visual results highlight the importance of our semantic deadline-aware bandwidth allocation algorithm, demonstrating its advantage in preserving image inpainting service quality.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper proposed a bandwidth resource allocation based on the semantic deadlines inherent in diffusion-based image inpainting models to optimize outcome quality. In this SGC framework, the transmitter sends two semantic information which are the semantic mask and textual description. Semantic mask provides positional information for transformations and the textual description specifies the content for modification. The receiver applies each semantic information asynchronously to its ongoing process as soon as they are received. Through simulations and visualizations, we demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed algorithm, highlighting its potential to enhance resource utilization efficiency and offer a new perspective for operating AI applications over communication networks.

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